
EXTENSION OF TWO SIMPLE FORMULAS BY RAMANUJAN

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ABSTRACT

This note presents an extension and observations on two simple formulas by Srinivasa Ramanujan. The aim is not to highlight any scientific application of these extensions but to celebrate the beauty of the original formulas created by this mathematical genius.

Keywords Number theory

1 Introduction

Ramanujan is one of the most prolific mathematicians of the 20th century, often considered a true genius of mathematics. With remarkable intuition, he left us a legacy composed of countless mathematical formulas. During his lifetime, he made around 6000 discoveries [1], which he recorded in notebooks. Decoding these notebooks kept many mathematicians busy throughout the 20th century [2]. This note does not aim to highlight results with practical utility, but rather to focus on the artistic side of certain mathematical formulas. These formulas, often simple and symmetrical, establish surprising connections between complex notions and more elementary ones. In my view, they are beautiful and artistic, especially when they manage to surprise even mathematicians with the relationships they reveal. An emblematic example is the equation $e^{i\pi} + 1 = 0$, which surprisingly connects several fundamental constants of mathematics.

In this perspective, I became interested in two of Ramanujan's simplest formulas, which I find particularly beautiful.

2 The two formulas of Ramanujan

2.1 First formula

$$\frac{9}{5} + \sqrt{\frac{9}{5}} \approx \pi \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{9}{5} + \sqrt{\frac{9}{5}} - \pi = 0.000048 \quad (2)$$

2.2 Second formula

$$e^{\pi\sqrt{58}} = 24591257751.999966 \approx 24591257752 \quad (3)$$

The formula (1) surprisingly relates the transcendental number π with a rational fraction and the square root of that same fraction, with good precision. The formula (3) on the other hand, connects a real number combining two transcendental numbers to an integer, with a good approximation.

I had fun exploring whether these formulas of Ramanujan could be extended to other real numbers. There's no need to have the genius of Ramanujan to explore these extensions today. With a small program, I highlighted the formulas below. To my knowledge, these expressions are not found in the literature.

3 Extension of the first formula

To extend the first formula of Ramanujan to other constants, I restricted my search to two natural numbers a and b in the interval $[1, 999]$, such that $\frac{a}{b} + \sqrt{\frac{a}{b}} \approx n$, where n is a remarkable constant [3]. This limitation to the interval $[1, 999]$ aims to preserve the simplicity of the formula, which is distinguished by its ease of memorization. By expanding the search interval, it would be possible to find several approximations of the target constants.

Here are the approximations of some remarkable constants obtained using Ramanujan's formula:

The Euler's constant e .

$$\frac{163}{109} + \sqrt{\frac{163}{109}} \approx e \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{163}{109} + \sqrt{\frac{163}{109}} - e = 0.00000175 \quad (5)$$

Gelfond-Schneider constant.

$$\frac{535}{367} + \sqrt{\frac{535}{367}} \approx 2^{\sqrt{2}} \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{535}{367} + \sqrt{\frac{535}{367}} - 2^{\sqrt{2}} = 0.00000119 \quad (7)$$

Gelfond's constant.

$$\frac{865}{46} + \sqrt{\frac{865}{46}} \approx e^{\pi} \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{865}{46} + \sqrt{\frac{865}{46}} - e^{\pi} = 0.000053 \quad (9)$$

Inverse of the square root of Gelfond's constant.

$$\frac{25}{801} + \sqrt{\frac{25}{801}} \approx e^{-\pi/2} \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{25}{801} + \sqrt{\frac{25}{801}} - e^{-\pi/2} = 0.0000022 \quad (11)$$

The constant $\frac{\log(3)}{\log(2)}$. For this number, several solutions exist; I choose the one that provides the best approximation.

$$\frac{474}{649} + \sqrt{\frac{474}{649}} \approx \frac{\log(3)}{\log(2)} \quad (12)$$

$$\frac{\log(3)}{\log(2)} - \frac{474}{649} - \sqrt{\frac{474}{649}} = 0.000000368 \quad (13)$$

The constant π^e . For this number, no solution was found with a precision strictly less than 10^{-4} . The best solution obtained is as follows:

$$\frac{564}{31} + \sqrt{\frac{564}{31}} \approx \pi^e \quad (14)$$

$$\frac{564}{31} + \sqrt{\frac{564}{31}} - \pi^e = 0.000219 \quad (15)$$

4 Observation on the second formula

Ramanujan observed that $e^{\pi\sqrt{58}} = 24591257751.999966 \approx 24591257752$

First, I wanted to extend this formula to determine whether other integers could be obtained in a similar way. Are there integers k such that $e^{\pi\sqrt{k}} \approx n$, where n is an integer? This work has been remarkably explored; see [4].

I explored another possible hidden property of these numbers. While I am unsure of the significance of this observation, I chose to share it. Mathematicians can determine whether it is trivial, already known, or indicative of a deeper property.

I observed that the prime factorization of the integer close to $e^{\pi\sqrt{58}}$ is as follows: $24591257752 = 8 \times 3073907219$. Notice that this number is divisible by 8 and by the prime number 3073907219.

I then sought to identify numbers of the form

$$\lceil e^{\pi\sqrt{k}} \rceil$$

that can be expressed in the same way as Ramanujan's number, i.e., as 8 multiplied by a prime number.

The values of k that satisfy this property are $k \in \{7, 9, 10, 18, 22, 25, 58\}$. This list is not exhaustive, as I limited my search to $k < 100$.

Furthermore, the numbers

$$\lceil e^{\pi\sqrt{k}} \rceil$$

that are divisible by 8 but not by 16 and can be expressed as $8 \times n$ where n is not a prime. These correspond to $k \in \{13, 19, 21, 27, 37, 43, 53, 63, 67, 72, 73, 76, 88, 92\}$

5 Conclusion

We observed that the formula $\frac{a}{b} + \sqrt{\frac{a}{b}}$ with a and b integers in $[1, 999]$, can be extended to some remarkable numbers. For a precision less than 10^{-5} , we found only one solution, except for $\frac{\log(3)}{\log(2)}$, for which multiple values of a and b give good results. By requiring a small margin of error in the approximation, some numbers cannot be approximated.

For example, π^e has no solution for a fixed error threshold of 10^{-6} . For a given precision and with a and b in the interval $[1, 999]$, which irrational numbers can be approximately written in the form of Ramanujan's formula? It is clear that the probability of finding a solution decreases for numbers that are too small or too large. The minimum and maximum values reachable by this formula are $\frac{1}{999} + \sqrt{\frac{1}{999}}$ and $\frac{999}{1} + \sqrt{\frac{999}{1}}$, respectively.

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